

```

GLM scenario1P1S1D1B1scenario2P1S1D1B2scenario3P1S1D1B3scenario4P1S1D2B1
scenario5P1S1D2B2
scenario6P1S1D2B3scenario7P1S1D3B1scenario8P1S1D3B2scenario9P1S1D3B3
scenario10P1S2D1B1
scenario11P1S2D1B2scenario12P1S2D1B3Tscenario13P1S2D2B1scenario14P1S
2D2B2 scenario15P1S2D2B3
scenario16P1S2D3B1scenario17P1S2D3B2scenario18P1S2D3B3scenario19P2S1
D1B1 scenario20P2S1D1B2
scenario21P2S1D1B3scenario22P2S1D2B1scenario23P2S1D2B2scenario24P2S1
D2B3 scenario25P2S1D3B1
scenario26P2S1D3B2scenario27P2S1D3B3scenario28P2S2D1B1scenario29P2S2
D1B2 scenario30P2S2D1B3
scenario31P2S2D2B1scenario32P2S2D2B2scenario33P2S2D2B3scenario34P2S2
D3B1 scenario35P2S2D3B2
scenario36P2S2D3B3
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Behaviour 3 Polynomial
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Physical.activity*Diagnosis Smoking.habits*Diagnosis Physical.activity*
Smoking.habits*Diagnosis
Physical.activity*Behaviour Smoking.habits*Behaviour Physical.activity*
Smoking.habits*Behaviour

```

Diagnosis*Behaviour Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour Smoking.habit
s*Diagnosis*Behaviour
Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour.

General Linear Model

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Dependent Variable		
1	1	1	1	scenario1P1S 1D1B1		
			2	scenario2P1S 1D1B2		
			3	scenario3P1S 1D1B3		
		2	1	2	1	scenario4P1S 1D2B1
					2	scenario5P1S 1D2B2
					3	scenario6P1S 1D2B3
		3	1	3	1	scenario7P1S 1D3B1
					2	scenario8P1S 1D3B2
					3	scenario9P1S 1D3B3
2	2	1	1	scenario10P1 S2D1B1		
			2	scenario11P1 S2D1B2		
			3	scenario12P1 S2D1B3T		
		2	1	2	1	scenario13P1 S2D2B1
					2	scenario14P1 S2D2B2
					3	scenario15P1 S2D2B3
		3	1	3	1	scenario16P1 S2D3B1
					2	scenario17P1 S2D3B2
					3	scenario18P1 S2D3B3

Within-Subjects Factors

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Dependent Variable		
2	1	1	1	scenario19P2 S1D1B1		
			2	scenario20P2 S1D1B2		
			3	scenario21P2 S1D1B3		
		2	1	2	1	scenario22P2 S1D2B1
					2	scenario23P2 S1D2B2
					3	scenario24P2 S1D2B3
				3	1	scenario25P2 S1D3B1
					2	scenario26P2 S1D3B2
					3	scenario27P2 S1D3B3
2	2	1	1	scenario28P2 S2D1B1		
			2	scenario29P2 S2D1B2		
			3	scenario30P2 S2D1B3		
		2	1	1	scenario31P2 S2D2B1	
				2	scenario32P2 S2D2B2	
				3	scenario33P2 S2D2B3	
		3	1	1	scenario34P2 S2D3B1	
				2	scenario35P2 S2D3B2	
				3	scenario36P2 S2D3B3	

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,249	43,328 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,751	43,328 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,331	43,328 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,331	43,328 ^b	1,000	131,000
Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,387	82,780 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,613	82,780 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,632	82,780 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,632	82,780 ^b	1,000	131,000
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,136	10,216 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,864	10,216 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,157	10,216 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,157	10,216 ^b	2,000	130,000
Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,760	205,353 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,240	205,353 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	3,159	205,353 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	3,159	205,353 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,021	2,775 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,979	2,775 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,021	2,775 ^b	1,000	131,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,021	2,775 ^b	1,000	131,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,012	,781 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,988	,781 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,012	,781 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,012	,781 ^b	2,000	130,000
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,038	2,546 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,962	2,546 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,039	2,546 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,039	2,546 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,009	,602 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,991	,602 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,009	,602 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,009	,602 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,040	2,712 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,960	2,712 ^b	2,000	130,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Pillai's Trace	,000	,249
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,249
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,249
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,249
Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,000	,387
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,387
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,387
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,387
Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,000	,136
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,136
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,136
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,136
Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,000	,760
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,760
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,760
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,760
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Pillai's Trace	,098	,021
	Wilks' Lambda	,098	,021
	Hotelling's Trace	,098	,021
	Roy's Largest Root	,098	,021
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,460	,012
	Wilks' Lambda	,460	,012
	Hotelling's Trace	,460	,012
	Roy's Largest Root	,460	,012
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,082	,038
	Wilks' Lambda	,082	,038
	Hotelling's Trace	,082	,038
	Roy's Largest Root	,082	,038
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Pillai's Trace	,549	,009
	Wilks' Lambda	,549	,009
	Hotelling's Trace	,549	,009
	Roy's Largest Root	,549	,009
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,070	,040
	Wilks' Lambda	,070	,040

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
	Hotelling's Trace	,042	2,712 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,042	2,712 ^b	2,000	130,000
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,193	15,497 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,807	15,497 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,238	15,497 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,238	15,497 ^b	2,000	130,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,020	1,312 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,980	1,312 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,020	1,312 ^b	2,000	130,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,020	1,312 ^b	2,000	130,000
Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,243	10,278 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,757	10,278 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,321	10,278 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,321	10,278 ^b	4,000	128,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,024	,799 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,976	,799 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,025	,799 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,025	,799 ^b	4,000	128,000
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,049	1,638 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,951	1,638 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,051	1,638 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,051	1,638 ^b	4,000	128,000
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,031	1,010 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Wilks' Lambda	,969	1,010 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Hotelling's Trace	,032	1,010 ^b	4,000	128,000
	Roy's Largest Root	,032	1,010 ^b	4,000	128,000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Hotelling's Trace	,070	,040
	Roy's Largest Root	,070	,040
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,000	,193
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,193
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,193
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,193
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,273	,020
	Wilks' Lambda	,273	,020
	Hotelling's Trace	,273	,020
	Roy's Largest Root	,273	,020
Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,000	,243
	Wilks' Lambda	,000	,243
	Hotelling's Trace	,000	,243
	Roy's Largest Root	,000	,243
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,528	,024
	Wilks' Lambda	,528	,024
	Hotelling's Trace	,528	,024
	Roy's Largest Root	,528	,024
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,169	,049
	Wilks' Lambda	,169	,049
	Hotelling's Trace	,169	,049
	Roy's Largest Root	,169	,049
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Pillai's Trace	,405	,031
	Wilks' Lambda	,405	,031
	Hotelling's Trace	,405	,031
	Roy's Largest Root	,405	,031

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Smoking.habits + Diagnosis + Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behaviour + Smoking.habits * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour + Diagnosis * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis ...

b. Exact statistic

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Epsilon ^b Greenhouse-Geisser
Physical.activity	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Smoking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Diagnosis	,477	96,358	2	,000	,656
Behaviour	,836	23,354	2	,000	,859
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	1,000	,000	0	.	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,891	14,976	2	,001	,902
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,969	4,029	2	,133	,970
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,952	6,462	2	,040	,954
Physical.activity * Behaviour	,973	3,516	2	,172	,974
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	,812	27,091	2	,000	,842
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	,946	7,187	2	,028	,949
Diagnosis * Behaviour	,280	164,849	9	,000	,613
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,783	31,576	9	,000	,886
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,881	16,459	9	,058	,944
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,768	34,192	9	,000	,876

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity^a

Measure: MEASURE_1

Within Subjects Effect	Epsilon ^b	
	Huynh-Feldt	Lower-bound
Physical.activity	1,000	1,000
Smoking.habits	1,000	1,000
Diagnosis	,660	,500
Behaviour	,869	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	1,000	1,000
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	,914	,500
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,985	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	,967	,500
Physical.activity * Behaviour	,989	,500
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	,851	,500
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	,963	,500
Diagnosis * Behaviour	,625	,250
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,914	,250
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,975	,250
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	,903	,250

Tests the null hypothesis that the error covariance matrix of the orthonormalized transformed dependent variables is proportional to an identity matrix.

a. Design: Intercept

Within Subjects Design: Physical.activity + Smoking.habits + Diagnosis + Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits + Physical.activity * Diagnosis + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis + Physical.activity * Behaviour + Smoking.habits * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour + Diagnosis * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour + Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour + Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis ...

b. May be used to adjust the degrees of freedom for the averaged tests of significance. Corrected tests are displayed in the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table.

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	322,526	1	322,526
	Greenhouse-Geisser	322,526	1,000	322,526
	Huynh-Feldt	322,526	1,000	322,526
	Lower-bound	322,526	1,000	322,526
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed	975,141	131	7,444
	Greenhouse-Geisser	975,141	131,000	7,444
	Huynh-Feldt	975,141	131,000	7,444
	Lower-bound	975,141	131,000	7,444
Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	745,354	1	745,354
	Greenhouse-Geisser	745,354	1,000	745,354
	Huynh-Feldt	745,354	1,000	745,354
	Lower-bound	745,354	1,000	745,354
Error(Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	1179,535	131	9,004
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1179,535	131,000	9,004
	Huynh-Feldt	1179,535	131,000	9,004
	Lower-bound	1179,535	131,000	9,004
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	212,941	2	106,470
	Greenhouse-Geisser	212,941	1,313	162,204
	Huynh-Feldt	212,941	1,321	161,222
	Lower-bound	212,941	1,000	212,941
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	2172,893	262	8,293
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2172,893	171,976	12,635
	Huynh-Feldt	2172,893	173,023	12,558
	Lower-bound	2172,893	131,000	16,587
Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	16563,047	2	8281,523
	Greenhouse-Geisser	16563,047	1,718	9643,283
	Huynh-Feldt	16563,047	1,738	9528,809
	Lower-bound	16563,047	1,000	16563,047
Error(Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	7582,287	262	28,940
	Greenhouse-Geisser	7582,287	225,002	33,699
	Huynh-Feldt	7582,287	227,705	33,299
	Lower-bound	7582,287	131,000	57,880
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	3,667	1	3,667
	Greenhouse-Geisser	3,667	1,000	3,667
	Huynh-Feldt	3,667	1,000	3,667
	Lower-bound	3,667	1,000	3,667

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Sphericity Assumed	43,328	,000	,249
	Greenhouse-Geisser	43,328	,000	,249
	Huynh-Feldt	43,328	,000	,249
	Lower-bound	43,328	,000	,249
Error(Physical.activity)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	82,780	,000	,387
	Greenhouse-Geisser	82,780	,000	,387
	Huynh-Feldt	82,780	,000	,387
	Lower-bound	82,780	,000	,387
Error(Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	12,838	,000	,089
	Greenhouse-Geisser	12,838	,000	,089
	Huynh-Feldt	12,838	,000	,089
	Lower-bound	12,838	,000	,089
Error(Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	286,162	,000	,686
	Greenhouse-Geisser	286,162	,000	,686
	Huynh-Feldt	286,162	,000	,686
	Lower-bound	286,162	,000	,686
Error(Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Sphericity Assumed	2,775	,098	,021
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,775	,098	,021
	Huynh-Feldt	2,775	,098	,021
	Lower-bound	2,775	,098	,021

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed	173,111	131	1,321
	Greenhouse-Geisser	173,111	131,000	1,321
	Huynh-Feldt	173,111	131,000	1,321
	Lower-bound	173,111	131,000	1,321
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	3,715	2	1,858
	Greenhouse-Geisser	3,715	1,804	2,060
	Huynh-Feldt	3,715	1,827	2,033
	Lower-bound	3,715	1,000	3,715
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	485,118	262	1,852
	Greenhouse-Geisser	485,118	236,288	2,053
	Huynh-Feldt	485,118	239,388	2,026
	Lower-bound	485,118	131,000	3,703
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	12,869	2	6,435
	Greenhouse-Geisser	12,869	1,941	6,631
	Huynh-Feldt	12,869	1,969	6,534
	Lower-bound	12,869	1,000	12,869
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	568,742	262	2,171
	Greenhouse-Geisser	568,742	254,241	2,237
	Huynh-Feldt	568,742	258,004	2,204
	Lower-bound	568,742	131,000	4,342
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	1,933	2	,967
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,933	1,908	1,013
	Huynh-Feldt	1,933	1,935	,999
	Lower-bound	1,933	1,000	1,933
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed	360,456	262	1,376
	Greenhouse-Geisser	360,456	249,883	1,442
	Huynh-Feldt	360,456	253,481	1,422
	Lower-bound	360,456	131,000	2,752
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	12,695	2	6,347
	Greenhouse-Geisser	12,695	1,948	6,517
	Huynh-Feldt	12,695	1,977	6,421
	Lower-bound	12,695	1,000	12,695
Error(Physical. activity*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	603,638	262	2,304
	Greenhouse-Geisser	603,638	255,191	2,365
	Huynh-Feldt	603,638	258,991	2,331
	Lower-bound	603,638	131,000	4,608

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking.habits)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	1,003	,368	,008
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,003	,361	,008
	Huynh-Feldt	1,003	,362	,008
	Lower-bound	1,003	,318	,008
Error(Physical. activity*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	2,964	,053	,022
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,964	,055	,022
	Huynh-Feldt	2,964	,054	,022
	Lower-bound	2,964	,087	,022
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis	Sphericity Assumed	,703	,496	,005
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,703	,490	,005
	Huynh-Feldt	,703	,492	,005
	Lower-bound	,703	,403	,005
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	2,755	,065	,021
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2,755	,067	,021
	Huynh-Feldt	2,755	,066	,021
	Lower-bound	2,755	,099	,021
Error(Physical. activity*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	175,500	2	87,750
	Greenhouse-Geisser	175,500	1,683	104,257
	Huynh-Feldt	175,500	1,703	103,065
	Lower-bound	175,500	1,000	175,500
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	1200,944	262	4,584
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1200,944	220,518	5,446
	Huynh-Feldt	1200,944	223,068	5,384
	Lower-bound	1200,944	131,000	9,168
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	4,130	2	2,065
	Greenhouse-Geisser	4,130	1,898	2,176
	Huynh-Feldt	4,130	1,925	2,145
	Lower-bound	4,130	1,000	4,130
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	521,092	262	1,989
	Greenhouse-Geisser	521,092	248,628	2,096
	Huynh-Feldt	521,092	252,179	2,066
	Lower-bound	521,092	131,000	3,978
Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	368,035	4	92,009
	Greenhouse-Geisser	368,035	2,451	150,131
	Huynh-Feldt	368,035	2,502	147,115
	Lower-bound	368,035	1,000	368,035
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	2169,298	524	4,140
	Greenhouse-Geisser	2169,298	321,137	6,755
	Huynh-Feldt	2169,298	327,721	6,619
	Lower-bound	2169,298	131,000	16,560
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	6,155	4	1,539
	Greenhouse-Geisser	6,155	3,544	1,737
	Huynh-Feldt	6,155	3,654	1,684
	Lower-bound	6,155	1,000	6,155
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	900,512	524	1,719
	Greenhouse-Geisser	900,512	464,234	1,940
	Huynh-Feldt	900,512	478,728	1,881
	Lower-bound	900,512	131,000	6,874
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	14,731	4	3,683
	Greenhouse-Geisser	14,731	3,774	3,903
	Huynh-Feldt	14,731	3,900	3,777
	Lower-bound	14,731	1,000	14,731

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	19,144	,000	,128
	Greenhouse-Geisser	19,144	,000	,128
	Huynh-Feldt	19,144	,000	,128
	Lower-bound	19,144	,000	,128
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	1,038	,356	,008
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,038	,353	,008
	Huynh-Feldt	1,038	,353	,008
	Lower-bound	1,038	,310	,008
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	22,225	,000	,145
	Greenhouse-Geisser	22,225	,000	,145
	Huynh-Feldt	22,225	,000	,145
	Lower-bound	22,225	,000	,145
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	,895	,466	,007
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,895	,457	,007
	Huynh-Feldt	,895	,459	,007
	Lower-bound	,895	,346	,007
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	1,955	,100	,015
	Greenhouse-Geisser	1,955	,104	,015
	Huynh-Feldt	1,955	,102	,015
	Lower-bound	1,955	,164	,015

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	986,825	524	1,883
	Greenhouse-Geisser	986,825	494,418	1,996
	Huynh-Feldt	986,825	510,912	1,931
	Lower-bound	986,825	131,000	7,533
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	4,157	4	1,039
	Greenhouse-Geisser	4,157	3,503	1,187
	Huynh-Feldt	4,157	3,611	1,151
	Lower-bound	4,157	1,000	4,157
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed	740,955	524	1,414
	Greenhouse-Geisser	740,955	458,893	1,615
	Huynh-Feldt	740,955	473,045	1,566
	Lower-bound	740,955	131,000	5,656

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source		F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Error(Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			
Physical.activity * Smoking. habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Sphericity Assumed	,735	,568	,006
	Greenhouse-Geisser	,735	,551	,006
	Huynh-Feldt	,735	,555	,006
	Lower-bound	,735	,393	,006
Error(Physical. activity*Smoking. habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Sphericity Assumed			
	Greenhouse-Geisser			
	Huynh-Feldt			
	Lower-bound			

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour
Physical.activity	Linear			
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear			
Smoking.habits		Linear		
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear		
Diagnosis			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear	
			Quadratic	
Behaviour				Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Behaviour)				Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear		
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear		
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear	
			Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear	
			Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear
				Quadratic
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity	Linear				322,526
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				975,141
Smoking.habits		Linear			745,354
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			1179,535
Diagnosis			Linear		120,167
			Quadratic		92,774
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		1578,375
			Quadratic		594,518
Behaviour				Linear	16441,000
				Quadratic	122,046
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	5212,208
				Quadratic	2370,079
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			3,667
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			173,111
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		2,175
			Quadratic		1,541
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		287,534
			Quadratic		197,584
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		10,341
			Quadratic		2,528
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		327,534
			Quadratic		241,208
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,591
			Quadratic		,342
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		183,450
			Quadratic		177,005
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	5,417
				Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	347,958
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	166,834
				Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	854,041
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	df
Physical.activity	Linear				1
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				131
Smoking.habits		Linear			1
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			131
Diagnosis			Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Behaviour				Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			131
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1
			Quadratic		1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		131
			Quadratic		131
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	131
				Quadratic	131

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean Square
Physical.activity	Linear				322,526
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				7,444
Smoking.habits		Linear			745,354
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			9,004
Diagnosis			Linear		120,167
			Quadratic		92,774
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		12,049
			Quadratic		4,538
Behaviour				Linear	16441,000
				Quadratic	122,046
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	39,788
				Quadratic	18,092
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			3,667
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			1,321
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		2,175
			Quadratic		1,541
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		2,195
			Quadratic		1,508
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		10,341
			Quadratic		2,528
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		2,500
			Quadratic		1,841
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,591
			Quadratic		,342
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,400
			Quadratic		1,351
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	5,417
				Quadratic	
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	2,656
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	166,834
				Quadratic	
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	6,519
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	F
Physical.activity	Linear				43,328
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			82,780
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		9,973
			Quadratic		20,442
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behaviour				Linear	413,217
				Quadratic	6,746
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			2,775
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,991
			Quadratic		1,021
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		4,136
			Quadratic		1,373
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		1,136
			Quadratic		,253
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	2,039
				Quadratic	3,729
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	25,590
				Quadratic	3,273
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Sig.
Physical.activity	Linear				,000
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			,000
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,002
			Quadratic		,000
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behaviour				Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,010
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,098
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,321
			Quadratic		,314
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,044
			Quadratic		,243
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,288
			Quadratic		,616
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	,156
				Quadratic	,056
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,073
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity	Linear				,249
Error(Physical.activity)	Linear				
Smoking.habits		Linear			,387
Error(Smoking.habits)		Linear			
Diagnosis			Linear		,071
			Quadratic		,135
Error(Diagnosis)			Linear		
			Quadratic		
Behaviour				Linear	,759
				Quadratic	,049
Error(Behaviour)				Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits	Linear	Linear			,021
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits)	Linear	Linear			
Physical.activity * Diagnosis	Linear		Linear		,008
			Quadratic		,008
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis)	Linear		Linear		
			Quadratic		
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis		Linear	Linear		,031
			Quadratic		,010
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)		Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis	Linear	Linear	Linear		,009
			Quadratic		,002
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis)	Linear	Linear	Linear		
			Quadratic		
Physical.activity * Behaviour	Linear			Linear	,015
				Quadratic	,028
Error(Physical.activity*Behaviour)	Linear			Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Behaviour		Linear		Linear	,163
				Quadratic	,024
Error(Smoking.habits*Behaviour)		Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear
				Quadratic
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear
				Quadratic
			Quadratic	Linear
				Quadratic

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Type III Sum of Squares
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	3,220
				Quadratic	,910
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	207,155
				Quadratic	313,937
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	236,002
				Quadratic	48,440
			Quadratic	Linear	78,667
				Quadratic	4,926
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	957,498
				Quadratic	500,643
			Quadratic	Linear	474,749
				Quadratic	236,407
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	1,381
				Quadratic	3,940
			Quadratic	Linear	,773
				Quadratic	,061
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	199,119
				Quadratic	305,477
			Quadratic	Linear	166,477
				Quadratic	229,439
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	13,047
				Quadratic	,864
			Quadratic	Linear	,228
				Quadratic	,591
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	297,953
				Quadratic	265,386
			Quadratic	Linear	197,522
				Quadratic	225,964
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,684
				Quadratic	1,516
			Quadratic	Linear	1,910
				Quadratic	,047
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	170,316
				Quadratic	276,068
			Quadratic	Linear	127,340
				Quadratic	167,230

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	df
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
			Quadratic	Linear	1
				Quadratic	1
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131
			Quadratic	Linear	131
				Quadratic	131

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean Square
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	3,220
				Quadratic	,910
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	1,581
				Quadratic	2,396
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	236,002
				Quadratic	48,440
			Quadratic	Linear	78,667
				Quadratic	4,926
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	7,309
				Quadratic	3,822
			Quadratic	Linear	3,624
				Quadratic	1,805
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	1,381
				Quadratic	3,940
			Quadratic	Linear	,773
				Quadratic	,061
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	1,520
				Quadratic	2,332
			Quadratic	Linear	1,271
				Quadratic	1,751
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	13,047
				Quadratic	,864
			Quadratic	Linear	,228
				Quadratic	,591
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	2,274
				Quadratic	2,026
			Quadratic	Linear	1,508
				Quadratic	1,725
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,684
				Quadratic	1,516
			Quadratic	Linear	1,910
				Quadratic	,047
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	1,300
				Quadratic	2,107
			Quadratic	Linear	,972
				Quadratic	1,277

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	F
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	2,036
				Quadratic	,380
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	32,289
				Quadratic	12,675
			Quadratic	Linear	21,707
				Quadratic	2,730
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	,908
				Quadratic	1,690
			Quadratic	Linear	,609
				Quadratic	,035
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	5,736
				Quadratic	,427
			Quadratic	Linear	,151
				Quadratic	,343
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,526
				Quadratic	,719
			Quadratic	Linear	1,965
				Quadratic	,037
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Sig.
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	,156
				Quadratic	,539
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,001
			Quadratic	Linear	,000
				Quadratic	,101
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	,342
				Quadratic	,196
			Quadratic	Linear	,437
				Quadratic	,852
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	,018
				Quadratic	,515
			Quadratic	Linear	,698
				Quadratic	,559
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,470
				Quadratic	,398
			Quadratic	Linear	,163
				Quadratic	,848
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Within-Subjects Contrasts

Measure: MEASURE_1

Source	Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Partial Eta Squared
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour	Linear	Linear		Linear	,015
				Quadratic	,003
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear		Linear	
				Quadratic	
Diagnosis * Behaviour			Linear	Linear	,198
				Quadratic	,088
			Quadratic	Linear	,142
				Quadratic	,020
Error(Diagnosis*Behaviour)			Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear		Linear	Linear	,007
				Quadratic	,013
			Quadratic	Linear	,005
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Physical.activity*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear		Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour		Linear	Linear	Linear	,042
				Quadratic	,003
			Quadratic	Linear	,001
				Quadratic	,003
Error(Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)		Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	
Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	,004
				Quadratic	,005
			Quadratic	Linear	,015
				Quadratic	,000
Error(Physical.activity*Smoking.habits*Diagnosis*Behaviour)	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	
				Quadratic	
			Quadratic	Linear	
				Quadratic	

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Measure: MEASURE_1

Transformed Variable: Average

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	183381,818	1	183381,818	1398,298	,000	,914
Error	17180,182	131	131,146			

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Physical.activity

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,473	,160	6,156	6,789
2	5,952	,181	5,594	6,309

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	,521 [*]	,079	,000	,364
2	1	-,521 [*]	,079	,000	-,678

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Physical.activity	(J) Physical.activity	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	,678
2	1	-,364

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,249	43,328 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,249
Wilks' lambda	,751	43,328 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,249
Hotelling's trace	,331	43,328 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,249
Roy's largest root	,331	43,328 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,249

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Physical.activity. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

2. Smoking.habits

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	5,816	,180	5,459	6,173
2	6,608	,163	6,286	6,930

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Smoking.habits	(J) Smoking.habits	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval
					Lower Bound
1	2	-,792 [*]	,087	,000	-,964
2	1	,792 [*]	,087	,000	,620

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Smoking.habits	(J) Smoking.habits	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	-,620
2	1	,964

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,387	82,780 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,387
Wilks' lambda	,613	82,780 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,387
Hotelling's trace	,632	82,780 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,387
Roy's largest root	,632	82,780 ^a	1,000	131,000	,000	,387

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Smoking.habits. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

3. Diagnosis

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	6,116	,164	5,792	6,441
2	6,015	,169	5,679	6,350
3	6,506	,194	6,122	6,890

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
					Lower Bound
1	2	,102	,055	,195	-,031
	3	-,390 [*]	,123	,006	-,689
2	1	-,102	,055	,195	-,234
	3	-,491 [*]	,115	,000	-,770
3	1	,390 [*]	,123	,006	,090
	2	,491 [*]	,115	,000	,212

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Diagnosis	(J) Diagnosis	95% Confidence Interval for ^b ..
		Upper Bound
1	2	,234
	3	-,090
2	1	,031
	3	-,212
3	1	,689
	2	,770

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,136	10,216 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,136
Wilks' lambda	,864	10,216 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,136
Hotelling's trace	,157	10,216 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,136
Roy's largest root	,157	10,216 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,136

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Diagnosis. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

4. Behaviour

Estimates

Measure: MEASURE_1

Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	8,604	,129	8,348	8,859
2	5,985	,219	5,553	6,418
3	4,047	,234	3,585	4,510

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Behaviour	(J) Behaviour	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for ...
					Lower Bound
1	2	2,618 [*]	,186	,000	2,167
	3	4,556 [*]	,224	,000	4,013
2	1	-2,618 [*]	,186	,000	-3,069
	3	1,938 [*]	,157	,000	1,556
3	1	-4,556 [*]	,224	,000	-5,100
	2	-1,938 [*]	,157	,000	-2,320

Pairwise Comparisons

Measure: MEASURE_1

(I) Behaviour	(J) Behaviour	95% Confidence Interval for ...
		Upper Bound
1	2	3,069
	3	5,100
2	1	-2,167
	3	2,320
3	1	-4,013
	2	-1,556

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the ,05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Multivariate Tests

	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Pillai's trace	,760	205,353 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,760
Wilks' lambda	,240	205,353 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,760
Hotelling's trace	3,159	205,353 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,760
Roy's largest root	3,159	205,353 ^a	2,000	130,000	,000	,760

Each F tests the multivariate effect of Behaviour. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

a. Exact statistic

5. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,049	,178	5,697	6,400
	2	6,896	,158	6,584	7,209
2	1	5,583	,192	5,203	5,963
	2	6,320	,179	5,966	6,673

6. Physical.activity * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	6,390	,159	6,075	6,705
	2	6,301	,166	5,973	6,628
	3	6,727	,189	6,353	7,102
2	1	5,842	,182	5,482	6,202
	2	5,729	,186	5,361	6,096
	3	6,284	,211	5,867	6,701

7. Physical.activity * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,933	,131	8,674	9,192
	2	6,191	,215	5,766	6,616
	3	4,294	,234	3,831	4,757
2	1	8,274	,151	7,975	8,573
	2	5,780	,232	5,321	6,240
	3	3,801	,243	3,320	4,281

8. Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	5,679	,183	5,316	6,042
	2	5,586	,185	5,220	5,951
	3	6,183	,210	5,767	6,599
2	1	6,553	,163	6,231	6,875
	2	6,443	,168	6,111	6,775
	3	6,828	,192	6,449	7,208

9. Smoking.habits * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,467	,156	8,159	8,776
	2	5,529	,240	5,054	6,004
	3	3,452	,247	2,963	3,941
2	1	8,740	,123	8,497	8,983
	2	6,442	,212	6,022	6,862
	3	4,643	,242	4,164	5,121

10. Diagnosis * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	8,659	,131	8,399	8,919
	2	6,032	,227	5,584	6,481
	3	3,657	,243	3,176	4,138
2	1	8,597	,137	8,326	8,867
	2	5,852	,231	5,395	6,310
	3	3,595	,243	3,114	4,076
3	1	8,555	,140	8,278	8,832
	2	6,072	,240	5,598	6,546
	3	4,890	,291	4,315	5,465

11. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
1	1	1	5,942	,182	5,581
		2	5,856	,186	5,488
		3	6,348	,210	5,933
	2	1	6,838	,163	6,515
		2	6,745	,168	6,412
		3	7,106	,188	6,735
2	1	1	5,417	,201	5,019
		2	5,316	,196	4,928
		3	6,018	,228	5,567
	2	1	6,268	,178	5,915
		2	6,141	,190	5,765
		3	6,551	,211	6,134

11. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	95% Confidence .
			Upper Bound
1	1	1	6,302
		2	6,224
		3	6,764
	2	1	7,162
		2	7,078
		3	7,477
2	1	1	5,814
		2	5,703
		3	6,469
	2	1	6,621
		2	6,518
		3	6,967

12. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
1	1	1	8,811	,160	8,494
		2	5,687	,246	5,201
		3	3,649	,247	3,160
	2	1	9,056	,125	8,808
		2	6,694	,211	6,278
		3	4,939	,249	4,447
2	1	1	8,124	,175	7,777
		2	5,371	,250	4,876
		3	3,255	,256	2,749
	2	1	8,424	,149	8,129
		2	6,189	,229	5,737
		3	4,346	,255	3,842

12. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Behaviour	95% Confidence .
			Upper Bound
1	1	1	9,127
		2	6,173
		3	4,138
	2	1	9,303
		2	7,111
		3	5,431
2	1	1	8,470
		2	5,866
		3	3,761
	2	1	8,719
		2	6,641
		3	4,850

13. Physical.activity * Diagnosis * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,989	,137	8,717	9,260
		2	6,205	,228	5,753	6,656
		3	3,977	,250	3,483	4,472
	2	1	8,977	,140	8,700	9,255
		2	6,076	,234	5,613	6,538
		3	3,848	,245	3,365	4,332
	3	1	8,833	,144	8,549	9,117
		2	6,292	,243	5,811	6,772
		3	5,057	,296	4,472	5,641
2	1	1	8,330	,162	8,009	8,650
		2	5,860	,248	5,369	6,350
		3	3,337	,254	2,834	3,840
	2	1	8,216	,163	7,894	8,538
		2	5,629	,248	5,138	6,119
		3	3,341	,256	2,833	3,848
	3	1	8,277	,169	7,942	8,611
		2	5,852	,256	5,346	6,358
		3	4,723	,304	4,122	5,325

14. Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	1	1	8,561	,158	8,247	8,874
		2	5,523	,263	5,002	6,044
		3	2,955	,265	2,431	3,478
	2	1	8,451	,168	8,118	8,784
		2	5,341	,253	4,840	5,842
		3	2,966	,259	2,454	3,478
	3	1	8,390	,167	8,059	8,721
		2	5,723	,265	5,199	6,248
		3	4,436	,313	3,816	5,055
2	1	1	8,758	,145	8,471	9,044
		2	6,542	,219	6,107	6,976
		3	4,360	,255	3,855	4,864
	2	1	8,742	,127	8,490	8,994
		2	6,364	,230	5,909	6,818
		3	4,223	,257	3,714	4,733
	3	1	8,720	,139	8,445	8,995
		2	6,420	,238	5,949	6,892
		3	5,345	,299	4,753	5,937

15. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Mean	Std. Error	95% ... Lower Bound
1	1	1	1	8,970	,161	8,651
			2	5,636	,277	5,088
			3	3,220	,275	2,675
		2	1	8,826	,172	8,486
			2	5,523	,270	4,988
			3	3,220	,262	2,702
		3	1	8,636	,185	8,271
			2	5,902	,279	5,349
			3	4,508	,319	3,877
	2	1	1	9,008	,171	8,670
			2	6,773	,237	6,304
			3	4,735	,271	4,198
		2	1	9,129	,137	8,858
			2	6,629	,241	6,153
			3	4,477	,269	3,945
		3	1	9,030	,143	8,747
			2	6,682	,245	6,197
			3	5,606	,314	4,985
2	1	1	1	8,152	,193	7,770
			2	5,409	,284	4,847
			3	2,689	,277	2,142
		2	1	8,076	,191	7,698
			2	5,159	,266	4,633
			3	2,712	,268	2,183
		3	1	8,144	,192	7,765
			2	5,545	,284	4,983
			3	4,364	,333	3,705
	2	1	1	8,508	,167	8,177
			2	6,311	,241	5,834
			3	3,985	,275	3,441
		2	1	8,356	,168	8,023
			2	6,098	,253	5,599
			3	3,970	,283	3,409
		3	1	8,409	,177	8,060
			2	6,159	,264	5,637
			3	5,083	,314	4,462

15. Physical.activity * Smoking.habits * Diagnosis * Behaviour

Measure: MEASURE_1

				95% Confidence .
Physical.activity	Smoking.habits	Diagnosis	Behaviour	Upper Bound
1	1	1	1	9,288
			2	6,185
			3	3,764
		2	1	9,166
			2	6,058
			3	3,737
		3	1	9,002
			2	6,454
			3	5,138
	2	1	1	9,346
			2	7,242
			3	5,271
		2	1	9,399
			2	7,105
			3	5,010
3		1	9,314	
		2	7,167	
		3	6,227	
2	1	1	1	8,533
			2	5,971
			3	3,237
		2	1	8,454
			2	5,685
			3	3,242
		3	1	8,523
			2	6,108
			3	5,022
	2	1	1	8,838
			2	6,787
			3	4,529
		2	1	8,689
			2	6,598
			3	4,530
3		1	8,759	
		2	6,681	
		3	5,705	